

54th Days of Preventive Medicine

International Congress

27-30. September 2022.

Niš, Serbia

BOOK OF ABSTRACT

Public Health Institute Niš

Faculty of Medicine,
University of Niš

Serbian Medical Society

Niš, 2022.

*122 years of Public Health Protection in Serbia
from regular preventive activities
to great challenges in COVID-19 pandemic time*

*122 године заштите јавног здравља у Србији
од редовних превентивних активности
до великих изазова у време пандемије COVID-19*

**PUBLIC HEALTH INSTITUTE NIŠ
FACULTY OF MEDICINE, UNIVERSITY OF NIŠ
SERBIAN MEDICAL SOCIETY, NIŠ**

**54TH DAYS OF PREVENTIVE MEDICINE
INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS**

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MAIN TOPICS

- **Environment and health**
- **Nutrition and health**
- **Microbiology today**
- **Current parasitosis**
- **Theoretical and practical problems of communicable diseases**
- **Theoretical and practical problems of non-communicable diseases**
- **Health promotion – challenges and solutions**
- **Preventive aspect of healthcare organization**
- **Application of information and communication tools in the health care system**

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2. ENVIRONMENTAL NOISE MONITORING IN NOVI SAD, 2021

Emil Živadinovic², Sanja Bijelovic^{1, 2}, Marija Jevtić^{1, 2}, Nataša Dragic^{1, 2}, Maja Lazovic²

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Objectives: Considering environmental noise as a public health problem, monitoring environmental noise, in order to assess noise annoyance of urban population, is one of the key step. Methods: During 2021, City of Novi Sad provided in total 87 daily (24-hour) noise measurements on eight measuring spots, while Public Health Institute of Vojvodina, according to legal basis and standardized / accredited methodology, taken 23 measurements during October – December. Results: Based on the results, daily noise indicator (L_{day}) was increased in 55% of measurements, evening noise indicator ($L_{evening}$) in 52%, and night noise indicator (L_{night}) in 67%, while 6-16% of the population during the day, i.e. 4-9% during the night (depending on the part of the city) were highly annoyed (%HA) by environmental noise, predominantly traffic noise. Observed by urban areas, the environmental noise levels are in accordance with norms in „city center and city traffic area“, also in „residential area“, while the noise levels were increased in „recreation area and hospital area“, „school area“ and „busines and residential areas“ Conclusion: The results indicate high levels of noise in the urban environment with the population annoyance, as a consequence, which represent the main issue and challenge for the public health system.

Keywords: environmental noise, monitoring, annoyance, population